

Hematology and Serum Biochemistry of Grower Pigs fed Graded levels of Empty Oil Palm Bunch Bioash as a mineral source

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Abstract: This study aimed to produce a low-potassium empty palm bunch ash (EPBA) and evaluate its effects on the hematology and serum biochemistry of grower pigs. Empty palm bunches were collected, cleaned, dried, and ashed, with the ash further treated to reduce potassium content. Minerals analyses of the diets were performed. The treated EPBA was included in pig grower diets at four levels: 0.0 kg (control, T1), 0.10 kg (T2), 0.15 kg (T3), and 0.20 kg (T4) per 100 kg of feed, replacing common salt (NaCl) in a completely randomized design. A 12-week feeding trial was conducted with forty-eight grower pigs, divided into four groups of 60 birds each, with three replicates per group. At the end of the feeding trials, blood samples were collected randomly from three pigs per treatment through the jugular vein using hypodermic needle and Syringe for hematological analysis and serum biochemistry. The 0.20 kg/100kg diet (T2) supplemented group recorded significantly higher Hemoglobin (11.38g/dl), and PCV values (39.47g/dl) than the control, and the other supplementation groups. Creatinine (1.20mg/dl) and Urea (23.00mg/dl) recorded in this study falls within the normal recommended range for grower pigs (0.8 – 2.3mg/dl creatinine; 8.20 – 24.6mg/dl urea). The study concludes that supplementing grower pig diets with treated palm bunch ash at 0.20 kg per 100 kg of feed improved hematological and serum biochemistry indices especially the hemoglobin and packed cell volume.

Keywords: Blood characteristics, Feed, Minerals, Grower pigs, Oil palm bunch ash

Introduction

Animal nutrition, health, physiology and biochemistry can be optimized essentially by mineral electrolytes (Unamba Oparah et al., 2017). The monovalent ions (K⁺, Na⁺, Cl⁻) among these electrolytes are the key ones involved in acid base balance of the fluids, thereby increasing permeability and absorption potentials in the digestive tract than divalent ions (Unamba Oparah et al., 2017; Nwogu et al., 2024). Hematological components are very important in monitoring feed toxicity, particularly of feed constituents that have direct effects on blood functions (Nwogu et al 2024). It has been shown that Empty Palm bunch (EPBA) is rich in essential minerals and has a unique physical nature (Okonkwo et al., 2018). Information about the use of plant ash as an additive in pig diets is limited.

The empty palm bunch (EPB) is a biomass waste product of the palm oil milling industry that constitutes about 20-23% of the oil milling residues. Globally, about 22.4 million tons of EPB are produced annually in palm oil producing countries (Noah, 2022). Conventional disposal channels available to the oil millers have not been absorbed substantially thereby posing a serious disposal challenge (Nwogu et al., 2023). Recent studies

by Ohanaka (2022) and Nwogu (2022) have shown that such biomass EPB-derived bioash could serve as functional feed additives for improving the performance of broilers chickens and laying hens respectively. The study was undertaken to produce a feed grade ash and to determine its effects on hematology and biochemical characteristics in grower pigs.

Materials and Methods

Study location

The study was carried out at the Teaching and Research Farm of University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo state. Imo state (04°04' - 06°15'N, 06°15' - 08°15'E) is situated in the South-eastern agro-ecological zone of Nigeria. Oil palm is the dominant tree crop in the study area.

Collection and preparation of PBA

Palm bunches from which fruits had already been harvested were collected from a palm oil mill located at Umuagwo in Ohaji Egbema LGA, Imo State, Nigeria. The empty palm bunches were gathered, washed with clean water to remove sand and other particles and sundried for seven days. Thereafter, the palm bunch was burnt to produce the ash. The ash was allowed to cool for a day and was weighed. It was further sieved to remove

unburnt parts and charcoal and thereafter mixed liberally with water in a plastic bowl to dissolve it. The mixture was allowed to settle about 2 days and thereafter, the solution at the top decanted while the solid was sieved through a cloth or polythene woven sack to remove the remaining liquid. It is assumed that since potassium and sodium are major macro mineral in the EPFB ash, reasonable percentages of these minerals will be dissolved in the discarded solution (Nwogu, 2022). The Undissolved ash material was sun dried for 4 to 6 days to achieve consistent moisture content of less than 10% and thereafter stored in a tightly sealed plastic container for analysis.

Preparation and analysis of experimental diets

Forty-eight grower pigs (9–11 weeks) was used for this experiment that lasted for 12 weeks. They were ear tagged for identification. Pigs were divided into four treatment groups of 12 pigs and each group was replicated three times in a completely randomized design. Four experimental diets were formulated and offered to the pigs such that the control diet did not contain the PBA, whereas the other three diets contained graded levels of the PBA at 0.10, 0.15, 0.20 kg/100kg for pig grower diets in partial replacement for common salt

(Table 1). All other ingredients were of equal proportions across the test diets. The nutrient values of the experimental diets will be calculated from the feed formulation table. Mineral analysis was determined according to the method described by AOAC international (2016).

Determination of hematological and serum biochemical characteristics

At the 12th week of the experiment, 10ml of blood samples were collected aseptically through the jugular vein from each pig per replicate. 4ml of the blood was discarded into EDTA-treated sterile Bior bottles to prevent clotting and for hematological analysis. The remaining 6 ml was discarded into sterile bottles and allowed to clot after which the serum was separated using standard clinical methods. Hematological characteristics of the birds such as red blood cell counts (RBC), hemoglobin concentration (HB), and packed cell volume (PCV), white blood cells (WBC) and their differentials were determined using Beckman Coulter Ac-T10 Laboratory hematology Blood Analyzer. The serum samples were used to determine the total serum protein, albumin, globulin, urea concentration, creatinine and cholesterol concentration, serum lipids and electrolytes using Bayer DCA 2000+ HbA1c Analyzer.

Table 1 Ingredient composition of PBA based diets in grower pigs

Ingredients	T1	T2	T3	T4
Maize	32.00	32.00	32.00	32.00
Soya bean meal	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
PKC (palm kernel cake)	55.00	55.00	55.00	55.00
Bone meal	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50
Premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Salt	0.25	0.15	0.10	0.05
Ash	-	0.10	0.15	0.20
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Nutrient calculated				
Crude protein (%)	17.28	17.28	17.28	17.28
Met. Energy (ME. Kal/kg)	2531	2531	2531	2531

Vitamin premix contains the following per kg of feed: Vit A = 5,000,000IU, Vit D3 = 1,000,000IU, Vit E = 1875IU, Vit K = 1255gm, Thiamin (B1) = 0.6255gm, Riboflavour = 1.875gm, Calcium panthothenate = 2.8kg, Nicotinic acid = 5.625gm, Pyridoxin = 0.625gm, Vit B12 = 5gm, folic acid = 0.31gm, Biotin = 0.1gm, Cholin chloride = 150gm, methionine = 75gm. Manganese = 5gm, Iron = 10gm, Copper = 1.5gm, Iodine = 0.5gm, Cobalt = 1.0gm, Selenium = 0.05gm, Antioxidiane 50gm, Antimold = 7.5gm, Nigrovin = 10gm, lysine = 75gm.

Data Analysis

Data collected on the different parameters was subjected to statistical analysis using analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and differences between the treatment means was compared using the Duncan s Multiple Range Test using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) User s Guide, Version 24.00. (SPSS, 2012).

Results and Discussion

Mineral concentrations in palm bunch ash mineral concentrations in the palm bunch ash

are shown in Table 2. The major minerals were K (164,300.00mg/kg), Ca (74,700.00mg/kg), P (37,800.00mg/kg) and Mg (41,800.00mg/kg) with Cadmium having the lowest (3.51mg/kg). The higher K, Ca and Mg recorded in oil palm bunch ash is in agreement with some previous work (Nwogu et al., 2014; Van Ryssen and Ndlovu, 2018; Ohanaka et al., 2022) that K, Ca, Mg and P are the major mineral components in plant ash, The high concentration of K indicate the possibility of these plants to be natural accumulators of potassium (Ohanaka et al., 2022).

Table 2 Mineral concentrations in the palm bunch ash

Parameters	Processed ash
P (mg/kg)	37,800
Ca (mg/kg)	74,700
Mg (mg/kg)	41,800
K (mg/kg)	164,300
Na (mg/kg)	11,800
Mn (mg/kg)	1817.54
Fe (mg/kg)	1448.22
Cu (mg/kg)	303.17
Zn (mg/kg)	507.92
Co (mg/kg)	0.00
Cr (mg/kg)	108.98
Cd (mg/kg)	3.51
Lead (mg/kg)	0.00

Hematological indices of grower pigs

The data on hemoglobin concentration (Hb), packed cell volume (PCV), red blood cell concentration (RBC), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) are presented in Table 3.

All the parameters showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference among treatments. Ash treated treatments yielded superior results in Hb (11.38g/dl), PCV (39.47g/dl) MCV (66.06fl) respectively. The values recorded by the various treatment groups fell within the

physiological range for normal pigs as supported by other authors (Etim et al., 2013; Coronado, 2014). When hematological values fall within the normal range established for animals, it is an indication that diets did not show any adverse effect during the experiment period. This is in contrast with the reports of Abonyi et al., 2015 that the hematological values of young pigs fed zinc oxide supplemented diets showed no significant ($p < 0.05$) difference among all the treatment groups.

Table 3 Hematology of grower pigs fed diets with palm bunch ash

Parameters	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
Hb (g/dl)	10.58 ^b	11.30 ^a	9.54 ^c	11.38 ^a	0.23
PCV (%)	36.31 ^b	30.28 ^d	34.44 ^a	39.47 ^a	1.00
RBC	6.13 ^a	5.57 ^b	5.68 ^b	6.04 ^a	0.07
MCV	58.09 ^c	53.52 ^d	60.07 ^b	66.06 ^a	1.36
MCH	17.11 ^c	20.18 ^d	16.37 ^d	18.27 ^b	0.44
MCHC	29.70 ^b	36.30 ^a	27.77 ^c	28.08 ^c	1.06
WBC	18133.33 ^b	14616.67 ^c	18903.33 ^a	12756.00 ^d	760.29

Means on the same row with different superscript are statistically different ($p < 0.05$)

Serum biochemical indices

The serum biochemistry of grower pigs fed graded levels of palm bunch ash revealed that urea and creatinine concentrations significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased in T4 birds. However, the values for creatinine (1.20mg/dl) and urea (23.00mg/dl) recorded in this study falls within the normal range of (0.8 2.30mg/dl creatinine), (8.20 24.6mg/dl Urea) recommended by Merck Veterinary Manual (2016). The normal physiology for creatinine suggests that there was no wasting or catabolism of muscle tissues and that the animals were not surviving at the expense of

body reserve (Ahamefuna et al., 2006). There was increased total protein suggesting an improvement in nutrient assimilation particularly protein due to positive effects of palm bunch ash through increased pancreatic enzyme stimulation (Duwa et al., 2020). Improved serum globulin concentration was observed at T2 and T3 which indicates improved nutrient availability and absorptive capacity. However, there was a reduction in the serum globulin in T4 birds. The observed total protein values fell within the reference range of 3.25g/dl to 7.61g/dl as reported by Rajurker et al. (2009) which suggest a stable health status.

Table 4 Serum biochemical indices of grower pigs fed diets with palm bunch ash

Parameters	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
Urea (Mg/dl)	19.00 ^b	21.00 ^a	18.00 ^b	23.00 ^a	0.44
Serum creatinine (Mg/dl)	1.10 ^a	0.90 ^b	1.00 ^b	1.20 ^a	0.06
Total Protein (g/dl)	6.10 ^b	6.90 ^a	6.40 ^{ab}	6.50 ^a	0.04
Albumin (g/dl)	3.30 ^a	3.10 ^a	2.80 ^{ab}	2.90 ^a	0.05
Globulin (g/dl)	2.80 ^c	3.80 ^a	3.60 ^{ab}	2.40 ^d	0.02
Cholesterol (g/dl)	101 ^c	112 ^b	121 ^a	110 ^b	0.86

Means on the same row with different superscript are statistically different ($p < 0.05$)

Conclusion

This study was aimed at utilizing plant waste (PBA) as a useful mineral source for efficient animal feeding. Oil Palm bunch biomass ash with reduced potassium and sodium was produced. Palm bunch ash supplementation did not have any adverse effects on the hematological and serum biochemical characteristics. It, however elicited superior Hb, PCV and serum protein concentration over the control pig values.

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